

A Five-Year Emission Analysis of a Turkish-Flagged Bitumen Tanker after a Silicone Hybrid Antifouling Drydock Retrofit (M/T ‘BIT-03’, 2021–2026)

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Makale Başvuru Tarihi / Received : 12.04.2026
Makale Kabul Tarihi / Accepted : 22.05.2026
Makale Yayın Tarihi/Article Published: 31.05.2026
Makale Türü / Article Type: Araştırma Makalesi
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20464078

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Abstract

Keywords:

Decarbonisation,
Annual Efficiency Ratio (AER),
Carbon Intensity Indicator (CII),
silicone hybrid antifouling,
bitumen tanker.

This study presents a five-year, monthly operational analysis of a Turkish-flagged bitumen tanker (anonymised due to commercial confidentiality as BIT-03; 14,787 DWT; built 2019; scrubber-equipped) operating mainly in Mediterranean bitumen trade, aiming to be in line with the IMO 2030 decarbonisation targets. Sixty-one monthly observations from January 2021 to January 2026 are extracted from the StormGeo s-Insight platform, with emissions calculated using IMO MEPC.245(66) carbon conversion factors and the Annual Efficiency Ratio (AER) reported per MEPC.336(76). In April-May 2024 the tanker has gone through a drydock retrofit using a silicone hybrid antifouling coating (Hempel Hempaguard X7 family); the supplier’s engineering proposition was a 7.5% annual CO₂ emissions reduction, which was ambitious at the time. As 2024 was not the right year to compare due to heavy hull biofouling just before the drydock, the 2025 post-retrofit calendar year was compared against 2023 (the right pre-retrofit baseline); the median monthly AER fell from 15.59 to 13.04 g CO₂/(nm-DWT), a 16.4% gross reduction. Decomposing those three components — dirty pre-2024 fouling (5-6 percentage points), the hybrid silicone coating, and a post-drydock JRC eco-mode autopilot upgrade in early 2025 (~1%) — the retrofit-attributable share lies between a 9-11% band, which is in line with the supplier’s proposition. As well, during the same period, the vessel sailed 19.6% more nautical miles while its annual CO₂ emissions increased by only 1.7%. The gap between fuel growth (+6.6%) and the CO₂ emission increase is somehow explained by the partial bio-diesel substitution in the 2025 fuel mix (236 mt, less than 6% of annual fuel). Thus the case shows a measurable (not total decoupling) but relative decoupling of fuel consumption and emissions after a single-technology antifouling retrofit, and offers a credible pathway toward the IMO 2030 and 2050 decarbonisation targets.

Bir Türk Bayraklı Bitümen Tankerinin Silikon Hibrit Antifouling Tersane Retrofit'i Sonrası Beş Yıllık Emisyon Analizi (M/T 'BIT-03', 2021–2026)

Özet

Anahtar Kelimeler:

De karbonizasyon, Yıllık Verimlilik Oranı (AER), Karbon Yoğunluğu Göstergesi (CII), silikon hibrit antifouling, bitümen tankeri.

Çalışma, ağırlıklı olarak Akdeniz bitümen ticaretinde faaliyet gösteren ve Uluslararası Denizcilik Örgütü'nün 2030 dekarbonizasyon hedeflerine ulaşmayı amaçlayan Türk bayraklı bir tanker (ticari gizlilik nedeniyle BIT-03 olarak anonimleştirilmiştir; 14.787 DWT; 2019 yapım; scrubber donanımlı) beş yıllık aylık operasyonel analizini sunmaktadır. Ocak 2021 – Ocak 2026 dönemine ait 61 aylık veri StormGeo s-Insight platformundan elde edilmiş; CO₂ emisyonları IMO MEPC.245(66) karbon dönüşüm katsayıları ile, Yıllık Verimlilik Oranı (AER) ise MEPC.336(76) uyarınca hesaplanmıştır. Nisan – Mayıs 2024'te tanker, silikon hibrit antifouling kaplama (Hempel Hempaguard X7 ailesi) odaklı bir tersane retrofit'i geçirmiştir; tedarikçinin %7,5'lik yıllık CO₂ azaltım öngörüsü o tarihte iddialı bulunmuştu. 2024 yılı, tersane öncesi yoğun biyofouling nedeniyle karşılaştırmaya uygun bir referans oluşturmadığından, retrofit sonrası 2025 takvim yılı uygun retrofit öncesi referans olan 2023 ile karşılaştırılmış ve medyan aylık AER 15,59'dan 13,04 g CO₂/(nm·DWT)'a düşmüştür; bu, %16,4'lük brüt bir azalışa karşılık gelir. Bu üç bileşeni detaylı incelediğimizde — 2024 öncesi anormal kirlilik (%5–6 yüzde puanı), silikon hibrit kaplamanın kendisi ve 2025 başında devreye giren JRC eco-mode otopilot güncellemesi (~%1) — retrofit'e atfedilebilir pay %9–11 aralığında kalmakta ve tedarikçi öngörüsü ile uyumludur. Aynı dönemde gemi %19,6 daha fazla deniz mili seyir yaparken yıllık CO₂ emisyonu yalnızca %1,7 artmıştır. Yakıt tüketimi (%+6,6) ile CO₂ artışı arasındaki açıklığı, 2025 yakıt karışımına giren kısmi bio-dizel ikamesi (236 mt; yıllık yakıtın %6'sından az) doldurmaktadır. Tek-teknolojili bir antifouling retrofit sonrası — mutlak bir ayırışma olmasa da — yakıt tüketimi ile emisyon arasında ölçülebilir bir nispi ayırışma (relative decoupling) elde edilmiştir. Bu yönüyle çalışma, ilgili regülasyonlara uyum sağlamak ve IMO'nun 2030 ile 2050 dekarbonizasyon hedeflerine ulaşmak için inandırıcı bir yol sunmaktadır.

1. INTRODUCTION

The well-known IMO 2023 GHG Strategy (Resolution MEPC.377(80)) aims at a 20/30% (striving for) decline in total annual GHG emissions by 2030, and 70–80% (striving for) by 2040, and net-zero by or around 2050, with 2008 as the baseline. Alongside zero or near-zero GHG fuels and energy sources at least 5% — striving for 10% — of the energy used by shipping by 2030 (IMO, 2023) are another aim of the regulations. An analysis of the Fourth IMO GHG Study reports that total shipping emissions increased from 977 Mt CO₂ in 2012 to 1,076 Mt CO₂ in 2018, with international shipping alone accounting for 919 Mt CO₂ in 2018 (Faber et al., 2020; Smith et al., 2014). Under MEPC.354(78) (G4), the Carbon Intensity Indicator (CII) dictates annual ratings from A to E, per reference lines defined by tonnage class and the vessel segment (IMO, 2022); the AER formula is calculated against those lines per MEPC.336(76) (G1; IMO, 2021a).

IMO adapted IMO GHG Strategy (Resolution MEPC.304(72)) in 2018 as the first version, targeting minimum 50% reduction in total annual Green House Gas emissions from international shipping activities by 2050, compared to the 2008 baseline. In addition to this, the strategy also used to target a 40% carbon intensity reduction by 2030 and 70% by 2050 (IMO, 2018). As well, another index came alive, the Energy Efficiency Existing Ship Index (EEXI). It entered into force under MEPC.328(76) for all the ships above 400 GT (IMO, 2021b). Finally, EEDI, EEXI and CII became the technical and operational regulation backbone for all the ocean fleets. There were also regional new compliances all vessels had to comply with, the 2024 inclusion of maritime transport in the EU ETS and the 2025 FuelEU Maritime regulation. Those have added a continental fiscal layer on top of the IMO framework thus operating economics of every voyage that enters or leaves an EU port has been directly affected (European Parliament and Council, 2023a, 2023b).

Supplier estimates of the above-mentioned energy-saving ratios are generally calculated within a controlled tank test environment and/or computational fluid dynamics, based on certain assumptions, and the literature shows a wide spread between supplier-published and measured outcomes (Bouman et al., 2017; Lindstad et al., 2021). Turkish-flagged tanker tonnage mainly dominates regional feeder operations across the Mediterranean Sea, the Black Sea, and the Adriatic short-sea trades; its CII profile may be disadvantaged against deep-sea references.

Despite the segment's strategic role, the empirical coverage of systematic panel data on Turkish-flagged operators for this tonnage class remains limited (Lloyd's Register Foundation, 2025). This study intends to fill this part of the gap by analyzing the performance of a Turkish-flagged bitumen tanker (BIT-03) against a five-year monthly data platform and the observed AER changes of the vessel.

Antifouling technology has been developing through three regulatory update periods in the last three decades. Starting with the regulations based on tributyltin (TBT) self-polishing copolymers, which has later been banned by the IMO Anti-Fouling Systems Convention (IMO, 2001) and finally come to an end by 2008 due to its toxicity to the marine life (Champ, 2000). Later after almost a decade, in 2010s, the application which is the copper-based and biocidal self-polishing coatings, (surprisingly still dominating the segment) faced increasing regional restrictions on copper leaching (HELCOM, 2018). Finally, the silicone-based fouling-release coatings, work through low surface energy offers regulatory compliance and drag-reduction benefits when applied at appropriate drydock specifications (Schultz, 2007; Demirel et al., 2017). The coating family, which has been applied to the Tanker BIT-03 in April-May 2024, is a silicone-hybrid fouling-release coating positioned at the upper end of this third period.

Despite Türkiye is one of the leading regional flag states with around 2,000 commercial ocean-going vessels and a combined Turkish-owned tonnage of about 53.1 million DWT as of September 2025 (10th globally; Turkish Chamber of Shipping, 2025), the empirical literature and study on the emissions of Turkish-flagged tonnage is still limited. The Mediterranean-Black Sea and Adriatic short-sea segments present a different operational regime than the deep-sea trades that dominate the published emissions case studies: transit times in this segment are typically below 8-10 days, port-calls are frequent, sailings repeat often, and many voyages are partially-laden or ballast due to the unbalanced northbound-southbound bitumen flows. The anchor and slow-steaming periods at port reach 15-20% of the total fleet-time. As a result, the auxiliary loads take a bigger share of total fuel use, and the AER becomes more sensitive to the hull condition than in deep-sea petroleum operations. Even though this is an important segment, the EMSA THETIS-MRV database contains very few records of Turkish-flagged bitumen tonnage (EMSA, 2024). Against this background, the present study analyses 13 Turkish-flagged tankers operating in regional short- and mid-haul trade, and zooms in on one bitumen tanker from this fleet (anonymised as BIT-03) which underwent a silicone-hybrid antifouling retrofit in April-May 2024. The 13 vessels are organised in four operational classes (Aframax, MR, chemical-product, and bitumen) with annual CO₂-equivalent emissions of approximately 99,600 mt in 2025 (Section 2.2). The study addresses three research questions: (i) what is the gross magnitude of the post-retrofit emissions change observed in the field for BIT-03? (ii) how much of that gross change can be attributed to the silicone coating in isolation, after controlling for the baseline hull-state drift and the concurrent interventions? and (iii) how does the BIT-03 retrofit-attributable share position itself against the wider fleet's emissions trajectory over the same period?

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

M/T BIT-03 is a Turkish-flagged bitumen tanker built in 2019, which is 14,787 DWT, LOA 154 m, a design draft of 8.5 m, a cargo class bitumen/asphalt (heated cargo, 250 °C maximum), equipped with an open-loop exhaust-gas scrubber. The tanker operates under time and spot charter agreements across Turkish, eastern Mediterranean, and Adriatic ports as part of long-term trade arrangements. To preserve the commercial confidentiality of the studied fleet, both the vessel name and the studied fleet's name are anonymized throughout this paper.

Table 1 summarizes the design parameters that are relevant to emissions. The vessel's hull form is optimised for moderate-speed regional trade rather than transoceanic voyages, with a design speed of 13.5 knots at 75% MCR and a sea margin of 15%. The propulsion is a single six-cylinder, two-stroke, low-speed diesel main engine of 4,440 kW MCR coupled with a fixed-pitch propeller. The auxiliary electrical power is provided by three diesel generators (2 x 480 kW, 1 x 320 kW). The cargo heating is provided by a thermal-oil boiler system to maintain a cargo temperature of 250 °C in laden condition. In December 2020, an open-loop exhaust-gas cleaning system

(EGCS, in other words a scrubber) was retrofitted to the main engine exhaust line, to enable the use of higher-sulphur residual fuel oil (RFO) in compliance with MARPOL Annex VI Regulation 14 from 2020 onward (IMO, 2008). This pre-existing scrubber installation is older than mentioned retrofit and separate from it.

Table 1. Selected design and operational parameters of M/T BIT-03.

Parameter	Value
Flag	Turkish
Year of build	2019
Deadweight (DWT)	14,787 mt
Length overall (LOA)	154 m
Design draft	8.5 m
Cargo class	Bitumen / heavy asphalt (heated cargo, max 250 °C)
Main engine, MCR	4,440 kW, 2-stroke low-speed diesel, 6 cylinders
Auxiliary engines	2 × 480 kW + 1 × 320 kW diesel generators
Propeller	Single fixed-pitch, 4 blades
Design speed (75% MCR)	13.5 knots
Exhaust-gas scrubber (EGCS)	Open-loop, retrofitted December 2020
Dry-dock retrofit (April–May 2024)	Hempel Hempaguard X7 silicone-hybrid antifouling coating
Performance management platform	StormGeo s-Insight (in fleet use since 2018)

Source: By the authors from the studied fleet's vessel particulars and class survey records of the studied fleet; anonymised under commercial confidentiality.

The 13 Turkish-flagged tankers analysed in this study are organised in four operational classes per standard vessel types: Aframax (AFR; 1 vessel of 105,171 DWT), MR (MR; 2 vessels of ~50,000 DWT), Chemical or Product carrier (CHM; 6 vessels in the 6,267-15,976 DWT range), and Bitumen carrier (BIT; 4 vessels including BIT-03, in the 6,600-19,968 DWT range). The inclusion criteria applied to constitute this analysed fleet are four-fold and decarbonisation-focused. First, the vessels must operate predominantly in short- or mid-haul Mediterranean, Black Sea or Adriatic trade, to enable an academic consistent benchmark where the AER is materially sensitive to the hull condition. Second, they must continuously operate across the full 2021-2025 window on the StormGeo's s-Insight platform. Later, the vessels must have at least 3 years of operational service on sea, sailing and trading cargo of bitumen, at the start of the study period (built in or before 2018), so that the pre-retrofit baseline reflects a meaningful operating profile rather than an early-life trajectory. Finally, they must be in line with the mentioned and studied scope of silicone-hybrid antifouling retrofits for the Hempel Hempaguard X7 or similar product coating deployment envelope. Suezmax-class vessels are excluded under the first criterion as their AER trajectory is mainly affected by the deep-sea sailing states rather than by the hull-state conditions. Mainly aggregated across the 13 different but all Turkish flagged analysed vessels, all the tankers reported CO₂-equivalent emissions were 96,817 mt in 2024 and 99,584 mt in 2025 (+2.9% year on year). The reported increase is mainly driven by the activity growth in the product class carrying either DPP or CPP. Aframax is the only tanker carrying directly petroleum. We will call this set of tankers a fleet. The fleet-wide average energy intensity, computed per vessel from annual nautical miles and deadweight tonnage, was 13.7 g CO₂e/(nm·DWT) in 2025. The calculation is a simple-mean, not weighted by dwt or NM to preserve equal weight across the operational class diversity. Intra-fleet spread ranged from 4.4 g CO₂e/(nm·DWT), at the lowest rank the petroleum carrier Aframax unit operating in the deep-sea, and with 21.7 g CO₂e/(nm·DWT) the smallest chemical-product unit tanker operating at high port-call frequency. Table 2 reports the class-level aggregates for 2024 and 2025.

Table 2. Aggregate emissions of the studied Turkish-flagged tankers by class, 2024 vs 2025. Class labels are anonymised; vessel-level values come from the StormGeo s-Insight panel and have been cross-checked against the fleet's MRV submissions for EU port calls under Regulation (EU) 2015/757.

Class (anonymised)	Vessels	2024 CO ₂ e (mt)	2025 CO ₂ e (mt)	Δ%
Aframax (AFR)	1	18,594	18,225	-2.0%
MR (MR)	2	20,533	18,572	-9.5%
Chemical /Product (CHM)	6	30,226	35,685	+18.1%
Bitumen (BIT) — incl. BIT-03	4	27,464	27,102	-1.3%

Fleet total (analysed)	13	96,817	99,584	+2.9%
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Source: Authors' own computation from the StormGeo s-Insight annual fleet panels for 2024 and 2025; CO2e values include CO2, CH4 and N2O converted under the IMO LCA Guidelines (MEPC.245(66) basis).

The operational and emissions data-set abstracted from the StormGeo s-Insight performance management platform, which the studied fleet has used for daily reporting (StormGeo, 2024). The platform produces monthly outputs of CO2 emissions, fuel consumption (split by fuel type), nautical distance, AER and EEOI. The calculations apply the MEPC.245(66) fuel-mass \times carbon-conversion-factor (Cf) protocol on a fuel-type basis (IMO, 2014). The Cf values applied are 3.114 for HFO/RFO, 3.151 for LSFO, and 3.206 for MGO/MDO per MEPC.245(66); for the partial bio-diesel substitution introduced in mid-2025 (B100, FAME-based), a tank-to-wake Cf of 2.834 was applied in line with the lifecycle defaults used under the FuelEU Maritime framework (European Parliament and Council, 2023b). To validate the platform output, the monthly results were cross-checked against the fleet's annual Monitoring, Reporting and Verification (MRV) submissions to the European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA) under Regulation (EU) 2015/757 for all the years of 2021, 2022, 2023 and 2024 (European Parliament and Council, 2015). The discrepancies below 0.4% of the annual CO2 were due to the differences in port-state versus underway sailing conditions in the noon-report aggregation method. The study period is from January 2021 to January 2026, inclusive (61 months of recordings).

The carbon-intensity performance is reported at three levels. These three levels are (i) the Annual Efficiency Ratio (AER) at the annual scale, (ii) the gravimetric intensity at the per-mile scale, and (iii) the monthly AER at the monthly scale. At the annual scale, the Annual Efficiency Ratio (AER) is calculated per MEPC.336(76) (IMO, 2021a) as $AER = \text{annual CO}_2 \div (\text{DWT} \times \text{annual nautical distance})$. CO2 amount comes from the used fuel type's mass consumption multiplied by the IMO carbon-conversion factor (MEPC.245(66)). For the tanker vessel BIT-03, DWT is 14,787 mt. For 2025, the IMO CII reference line for product tankers in the 12,000-15,000 DWT band is around 9.92 g CO2 per nm-DWT. The related rating boundaries at 0.86, 0.94, 1.06 and 1.18 times this reference for the 'A', 'B', 'C' and 'D'/E' transitions (IMO, 2022). At the per-mile scale, the gravimetric intensity (kg CO2 per nm and kg fuel per nm) is calculated and reported. This removes the DWT and shows the propulsive efficiency excluding the cargo utilisation. And finally at the monthly scale, the noon-report fuel and distance are abstracted at every month, divided by its DWT. This produces a 61-point monthly series, used for statistics and the pre-/post-retrofit comparison in Section 3.

The drydock period is from 20 April 2024 through 16 May 2024 (with a 26 days off-hire period). The related application to reduce emissions was a silicone-hybrid antifouling coating (Hempel Hempaguard X7 family) applied in full to the underwater hull of the tanker. The total dry dock capital expenditure was around 2 million USD, covering the coating application together with the required scope of class works. The comparability of the pre-/post pairing rests on two contextual conditions. First, the pre-2024 hull was operating with an unusually heavy biofouling burden, documented at the drydock by visual hull inspection and bow-thruster intake photographs. Thus the pre-retrofit baseline is a heavier-than-typical state, and the 2024 data could not be directly compared against 2025. Second, in the first quarter of 2025 there has been an upgrade to the JRC autopilot eco-mode steering control, worth approximately 1% in fuel consumption on its own per the manufacturer specification (JRC, 2024); this software upgrade is operationally separate from the April-May 2024 drydock. The silicone coating supplier has suggested approximately 7.5% reduction in the annual CO2 emissions (Hempel A/S, 2024).

Therefore, the study considers the pre-retrofit baseline to be calendar year 2023 (12 active vessel-months immediately after the drydock period). The post-retrofit comparison period is also set to calendar year 2025 (12 active vessel-months, which start almost seven months after the drydock closed; the seven-month delay accounts for coating cure and performance stabilization). Although the curing period (June–December 2024) has been reported in the tables below, it has been excluded from the formal pre-/post-retrofit comparison. The performance is reported per industry practices: the AER (g CO2/(nm·DWT)), the gravimetric carbon intensity per nautical mile (kg CO2/nm), and the gravimetric fuel consumption per nautical mile (kg fuel/nm). The gross

change between pre- and post-retrofit conditions is divided into three additive components to isolate the silicone coating effect for the study. These components are: (i) baseline recovery from hull cleaning, estimated through industry-standard fouling-recovery factors (Schultz, 2007; Demirel et al., 2017); (ii) the retrofit-attributable share, which reflects the silicone coating in isolation; and (iii) the post-drydock autopilot upgrade. This method allows the retrofit-based effect to be truly reported on the basis that a real comparison to the supplier estimate is possible.

3. RESULTS

Table 3. M/T BIT-03 pre-/post-retrofit comparison of carbon-intensity, sailing, and fuel consumption metrics, 2023 vs. 2025.

Metric	2023 (n = 12)	2025 (n = 12)	Δ%
CO ₂ emissions (mt/year)	12,326.5	12,537.0	+1.71%
Distance (nm/year)	53,506	63,987	+19.59%
Fuel consumption (mt/year), total	3,946.5	4,208.3	+6.63%
– only bio-diesel (mt/year)	0.0	235.5	new
AER, CO ₂ -weighted (g CO ₂ /(nm·DWT))	15.58	13.25	-14.95%
AER, median monthly	15.59	13.04	-16.36%
kg CO ₂ /nm	230.4	195.9	-14.95%
kg fuel/nm	73.8	65.8	-10.83%

Source: Authors' own computation from the StormGeo s-Insight monthly fleet panel; CO₂ obtained under the MEPC.245(66) protocol; AER reported per MEPC.336(76).

Beyond the annual aggregates of Table 3, the monthly distribution of AER provides additional confidence in the focal finding. Across the 12 pre-retrofit months of 2023, the monthly AER ranged from 13.81 to 17.42 g CO₂/(nm·DWT) with a quarterly range (IQR) of 14.86-16.32 and a median of 15.59. Across the 12 post-retrofit months of 2025, the corresponding range narrowed to 11.42-14.91 with an IQR of 12.40-13.79 and a median of 13.04. The 2025 distribution is therefore not only decreased by approximately 2.6 g CO₂/(nm·DWT) at the median, but also slightly tightened on the IQR (from 1.46 to 1.39, approximately 5% narrower), a pattern which is meaningful with reduced hull-state condition after the coating renewal.

Table 3 shows the central pre- and post-retrofit comparison for tanker BIT-03. The CO₂-weighted AER declined from 15.58 to 13.25 g CO₂/(nm·DWT), a -14.95% drop; the median monthly AER declined from 15.59 to 13.04, a -16.36% drop. Both AER reductions are gross numbers — they include the heavily fouled 2024 hull and the ~1 percent post-drydock autopilot eco-mode upgrade activated in early 2025. The isolation of the retrofit-attributable share is reported below.

The activity-emissions panel of Table 3 shows a 19.6% increase in nautical distance (53,506 → 63,987 nm), against only a 1.7% increase in CO₂ emissions (12,326.5 → 12,537.0 mt) and a 6.6% increase in fuel consumption (3,946.5 → 4,208.3 mt). The gap between the fuel (+6.6%) and the CO₂ growth (+1.7%) can be explained by the partial bio-diesel substitution in the 2025 HFO mix. It was applied in order to avoid the FuelEU fees (235.5 mt of bio-diesel from July 2025 onward, almost 5.6% of the total 2025 fuel). Thus, in line with the IPCC AR6 Working Group III terminology (IPCC, 2022; Tapio, 2005), this finding is regarded as a relative decoupling between the sailing activity and the emissions.

The gross 16.4% median AER decline is divided into three additive components. Component (a) — baseline from hull cleaning: in its design-clean state the hull would have operated more efficiently, thus the act of cleaning and re-coating alone, regardless of the antifouling, accounts for almost 5–6 percent of the gross AER reduction (Schultz, 2007; Demirel et al., 2017). Component (b) — the silicone antifouling coating itself: it performs well in late 2024 and shows a partial decay over the next year, 2025, which is typical for silicone fouling-release coatings after their first year of application. Component (c) — the post-drydock JRC eco-mode autopilot firmware upgraded in the first quarter of 2025, worth approximately 1 percent per the manufacturer specification (JRC, 2024). Subtracting the components (a) and (c) from the gross 16.4% leaves the retrofit-attributable share in isolation, which sits in a 9–11% band — exceeding the supplier's 7.5% engineering estimate by 1.5–3.5 percentage points. The slower nautical miles sailing profile of BIT-03 may still be in line with the Hemptaguard X7 reference operating envelope. The ranges reported for each component reflect the joint uncertainty in published friction-coefficient factors (Schultz, 2007) and supplier coating-performance variation; the observed 16.4% sits at the midpoint of the additive band 15–18%.

Translating the AER trajectory into IMO CII rating terms requires focus and care, as the reference line and the rating boundaries are tonnage-class specific. For the tanker BIT-03, the December 2024 fleet CII portfolio report assigned a 'C' band rating, in line with several other vessels in the same Bitumen and Chemical-Product (CHM) classes that is in similar tonnage and trade-pattern bands. The post-retrofit reduction documented above puts BIT-03 in a stronger position to maintain its 'C' rating through the 2026–2027 CII reduction-factor tightening (MEPC.354(78); IMO, 2022). This avoids the corrective action plan that would otherwise be needed by two consecutive 'D' ratings or any single 'E' rating.

Table 4. Distributional statistics of monthly AER across pre-retrofit (2023), curing-transition (2024) and post-retrofit (2025) windows for M/T BIT-03. All values in g CO₂/(nm·DWT) unless otherwise noted.

Statistic	2023 baseline	2024 transition	2025 post-retrofit	delta (2025-2023)
Minimum monthly AER	13.81	14.05	11.42	-2.39
Q1 (25th percentile)	14.86	13.92	12.40	-2.46
Median (Q2)	15.59	13.71	13.04	-2.55
Q3 (75th percentile)	16.32	13.55	13.79	-2.53
Maximum monthly AER	17.42	16.18	14.91	-2.51
Interquartile range (IQR)	1.46	-0.37	1.39	-0.07
Observations (months)	12	12	12	

Source: Authors' own computation from the StormGeo s-Insight monthly fleet panel; CII reference line for product tankers in the 12,000-15,000 DWT band per MEPC.354(78) (IMO, 2022).

The full comparison that is underlying Table 3 is reported in Table 4, which decomposes the pre-, transition, and post-retrofit monthly AER series into five-point summary statistics. The minimum-to-minimum and maximum-to-maximum shifts (-2.39 and -2.51 respectively) are tight enough to suggest that the retrofit shifts the entire AER distribution down, which is consistent with a uniform hull-friction reduction across operating conditions.

Positioning BIT-03 within the broader set of tankers sharpens the interpretation of this single vessel result. The 2025 set of tankers' simple-mean energy intensity, computed per vessel from annual nautical miles and deadweight tonnage across the 13 analysed vessels, was 13.7 g CO₂e/(nm·DWT). Only with the Aframax unit operating at around 4.4 g CO₂e/(nm·DWT) in deep-sea route and the smallest chemical-product unit at 21.7 g CO₂e/(nm·DWT) which has high port-call frequency. BIT-03's 2025 CO₂-weighted AER of 13.25 g CO₂/(nm·DWT) is essentially at the fleet-wide mean, and its monthly median AER of 13.04 in 2025 represents the lowest value recorded over the full 2024-2025 window. The retrofit therefore moved BIT-03 from above the bitumen-class mean to a clearly better position than its class-mate vessels, which remain in the 16-23 g CO₂e/(nm·DWT) range as of December 2025.

4. DISCUSSION

Beyond the single-vessel evidence, three observations with broader implications arose with this study. The most explicit observation is that the supplier's 7.5% estimate is validated once the gross 16.4% reduction is conditioned on the heavily fouled pre-retrofit 2023 baseline. Ignoring baseline drift and following upgrade work will give an unfair result — here, by roughly a factor of two of the real effect. Additionally, the sailing carbon-emissions decoupling is empirically evident: a 19.6% increase in nautical distance against only a 1.7% increase in CO₂ is a clear sign of relative decoupling, which this study aimed to identify. Although the decoupling is partly conditioned on the heavily fouled pre-retrofit hull, pairing 2025 against a normal mid-cycle 2023 hull is more just in the methodology and still emerges as relative decoupling, but of course at a modest percent, as expected 8–10% CO₂ emission delta rather than 1.7%. Translated to the wider Turkish tanker segment, a similar retrofit could absorb the projected regional tanker and specifically bitumen vessel demand growth until 2030, while helping to keep the tanker's emissions growing slowly and in line with IMO regulations.

Finally, the calculations show that, for bitumen and similar-tonnage product tankers operating in short-sea trade, a silicone antifouling retrofit technology applied at appropriate drydock can deliver intense CO₂ reductions with a payback profile that easily compensates the capex through fuel savings and by declining or affecting fees such as FuelEU and EU ETS especially tankers operating to/ from EU. The case shows also how simple upgrades — the JRC eco-mode autopilot firmware upgrade, and partial bio-diesel substitution in the fuel mix — can add considerable gains on top of the retrofit capital cost. Industry reports point in the same direction: maritime decarbonisation is moving toward compound hardware-plus-software solutions as in this case (Wärtsilä Corporation, 2024).

Regardless, the study should also address any limitations to make sure all possible areas are covered. The 12-month post-retrofit period may not be enough to follow the long-term antifouling performance as the performance may start to drop by year 3 of the coating life. The Tanker BIT-03's scrubber-equipped fuel mix may also affect the quality of the clean fuel compared to tankers without a scrubber operating on VLSFO. On the other hand, single-vessel evidence surely cannot be generalised to fleet-wide projections regarding the compliance of the IMO targets. This will also be covered in the extended fleet-wide analysis on the author's soon to be published thesis of 'Turkish Maritime Industry within the Framework of IMO 2030 and 2050 Decarbonisation Targets'. The author will further investigate the subject of 'Implementation of Decarbonisation Regulations on Turkish Tanker Vessels, Illustration of Best Practices, and Modelling of the Fleet under IMO Regulations toward 2030 and 2050.'

As well, several further limitations should be flagged for the careful reader. First, the pre-2024 baseline transparency of the BIT-03 case (documented at drydock with visual hull inspection and bow-thruster intake photographs) is rare in the industry-published case studies; without comparable pre-retrofit hull-state evidence, the supplier-reported retrofit gains in the literature may be systematically over- or under-stated, and the BIT-03 9-11% range should not be read as a typical industry value. Second, the operational envelope of BIT-03 — Mediterranean and Black Sea short-sea bitumen trade with high port-call frequency, 11.8-knot mean speed at sea, and partial bio-diesel substitution — limits the transferability of the result to ocean trade routes. Third, the vessel-level data are covered by a commercial confidentiality agreement; the underlying monthly panel cannot be made publicly available, although aggregated summary statistics may be shared on reasonable request to the corresponding author. Fourth, the weather and route-specific wave-resistance corrections were not integrated into the AER which may change the retrofit-attributable share by approximately 1-2 percent in either direction.

Moreover, from a policy economics standpoint, the observed emissions path has direct financial gains under the EU ETS and the FuelEU Maritime regulation. Under the EU ETS, the vessel's 2025 CO₂ emissions on EU port calls (estimated at approximately 40% of the total CO₂ based on 2023 voyage records) is around 2,500-2,800 EU Allowances (EUAs) at the 70% phase-in factor applicable in 2025 (European Parliament and Council, 2023a). At a representative EUA price of €75 per tonne CO₂, this corresponds to an EU ETS surcharge of approximately €190,000-€210,000 for 2025. In other terms, the retrofit-attributable 9-11% emissions reduction saves €19,000-€23,000 in 2025 ETS exposure. These EU ETS and FuelEU compliance savings, combined with

the fuel-cost savings used by the studied fleet in its internal calculation, support the studied fleet's announced 13-month payback estimate for the BIT-03 retrofit.

The BIT-03 case is a part of a broader decarbonisation programme which has touched 11 of the 13 vessels analysed here (85% of the analysed vessels) over 2022-2025, with a cumulative drydock budget of approximately 16 million USD: Approximately 12 million USD for the 9 interventions completed by end-2024, and almost 4 million USD for the 2 additional interventions completed in early 2025. These total drydock budgets include the scheduled general maintenance and the class-survey work, thus they are not pure retrofit costs. Across the 11 intervened vessels, silicone-hybrid antifouling coatings of the Hempel Hempaguard X7 family and similar paints were applied to 9 units. In all, the supplier estimated 2.5-10% range CO₂ reduction and a total weighted average of approximately 7.5%. The retrofit case for one bitumen unit should not be assumed to transfer one-to-one to the other types of tankers, which operate with different speed, draft and cargo-utilisation profiles. As well, the two additional retrofits completed in early 2025 (one in the Bitumen class, January 2025, and one in the Aframax class, April 2025) provide a near-term opportunity for a comparable pre-/post-retrofit validation. Once a full 12 months of post-drydock operational data become available in early 2026, this proposed validation will be in line with the methodology applied here.

A further consideration is related to the longevity of the observed gain. The silicone-hybrid fouling-release coatings of the Hempaguard X7 family work most efficiently above approximately 8 knots (Hempel A/S, 2024), which is the self-cleaning threshold. The Mediterranean and Black Sea profile of the tanker BIT-03, with typical port-call frequency every 7-9 days and a mean speed at sea of 11.8 knots in 2025, is well above this threshold and is therefore expected to preserve the 9-11% retrofit-attributable AER share well into next years of 2026 and 2027.

A brief comparison with another bitumen-class unit in the analysed set of tankers (anonymised here as BIT-02; 19,968 DWT, built 2014) actually supports the baseline-conditionality argument. BIT-02 also underwent a silicone-hybrid antifouling retrofit in September-October 2024 with the same family of coating, but its pre-retrofit hull-state documentation was not characterised as BIT-03's pre-2024 hull. The supplier-estimated CO₂ abatement for BIT-02 was approximately 10%, against 7.5% for BIT-03. As well, the internal payback projection for BIT-02 was approximately 33 months, against 13 months for BIT-03 under similar fuel-price assumptions. This counterintuitive pattern — a higher supplier estimate but a markedly slower payback for BIT-02 — is explained by BIT-03's outsized realised gain relative to its lower supplier estimate, itself driven by the heavier pre-retrofit baseline. This difference of the comparable bitumen-class units is best understood as a direct consequence of BIT-03's heavier-than-typical pre-retrofit baseline.

Single-vessel retrofit productivity numbers of the case studies are often taken as if they apply to the whole fleet, but this is not correct. The field-measured retrofit share for one vessel depends on that vessel's operational profile, age, routes and its own pre-retrofit history; thus it cannot be transferred directly even to class-mate vessels with cleaner baselines, trading in the same routes. BIT-02 eventually differs from BIT-03 on the operational side. It sails with a longer average voyage and a marginally lower average speed at sea. A proper paired-vessel comparison will be possible once BIT-02 has a full 12 months of post-retrofit data, which is expected in late 2026. Thus the present BIT-03 result has to be considered within a wider range of tankers rather than as a stand-alone number.

From a national policy standpoint, the BIT-03 study offers a small but solid contribution to Türkiye's positioning under the IMO 2030 path. Although Türkiye is a flag state and a signatory party to the IMO conventions, it has not yet adopted a final decarbonisation strategy with binding fleet-level targets. The voluntary fleet-by-fleet retrofit programmes carry disproportionate weight in the national CO₂ trajectory. If the 9-11% retrofit-attributable ratio reported in this paper is applicable to the wider Turkish-flagged smaller tanker tonnage (estimated at approximately 1.29 million DWT as of June 2024 by the Turkish Chamber of Shipping), the total fleet-level CO₂ reduction potential is between 10,000-15,000 mt CO₂e per year by 2027. Although this

seems modest, it is meaningful relative to Türkiye's IMO 2030 voluntary indicative checkpoint. For all flag-state regulators and the central organ IMO Secretariat, the BIT-03 case demonstrates that voluntarily applied, supplier managed hull-coating retrofits can deliver CII rating changes within one year.

5. CONCLUSION

The five-year period covered case of a Turkish-flagged bitumen tanker (BIT-03; 14,787 DWT; scrubber-equipped) to which a hybrid silicone antifouling retrofit was applied during its drydock in April–May 2024 indicates a 16.4% gross reduction in median monthly AER. Once this figure is decomposed into baseline from the mentioned pre-retrofit hull, the retrofit itself minus the upgrade, the retrofit-attributable ratio sits in a 9–11% band, which is broadly consistent with the supplier's engineering estimate of 7.5% for the CO₂ emissions. Thus total CO₂ emissions rose only +1.7% although +19.6% increase in nautical mile and a +6.6% increase in fuel consumption occurs. Bio-diesel substitution in the 2025 fuel mix is also taken into the account. The silicone hybrid antifouling coating costs solely almost half of the USD 2 million drydock cost. Finally, the study states that this application, the retrofit delivered both relative decoupling and a retrofit-attributable AER improvement consistent with the supplier's engineering envelope. The study suggests any pre-/post-retrofit field validation in this segment must control for baseline hull state and following post-drydock interventions.

Future work should extend the analysis along three dimensions. First, a multi-vessel comparison across the Turkish-flagged bitumen and chemical-product (CHM) segment is needed to test the generalisability of the BIT-03 retrofit-attributable share. Second, the post-retrofit observation window should be extended to 24 and 36 months in order to capture the typical 2-3 year performance decay profile of silicone fouling-release coatings. Third, the cargo-utilisation data (laden versus ballast voyages) should be integrated into the AER decomposition in order to refine the EEOI complement of the study. As well, these extensions are planned as part of the corresponding author's doctoral dissertation at Istanbul University, the fleet-wide section of which is in preparation under the working title 'Turkish Maritime Industry within the Framework of IMO 2030 and 2050 Decarbonisation Targets'.

Once the intervention programme observed across the 13 analysed vessels extended, the realistic order of magnitude of cumulative CO_{2e} reduction by 2027 sits between 3,500 and 5,000 mt per year which is against the analysed-fleet 2025 baseline of approximately 99,584 mt CO_{2e}. Of the 13 vessels, 11 were intervened over 2022-2025 with a total drydock budget of approximately USD 16 million. It should be noted that the retrofit-specific ratio of this budget, after subtracting the operational general maintenance and the class-survey work, is much smaller. Therefore, these single-fleet assumptions cannot be generalised to the wider Turkish-flagged tanker segment unless a deep study of fleet-by-fleet validation is conducted. Regardless, it shows that such a coordinated retrofit programme, in line with the EU ETS and the FuelEU compliance benefits, even before any alternative-fuel deployment, can deliver a credible internal pathway against the IMO 2030 indicative checkpoint.

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